

REVAMPING TEACHER EDUCATION IN THE LIGHT OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

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Abstract

Teacher is the backbone of educational system of a country. Quality of the teacher determines the quality of education prevailing in the country .Being the nation builder a teacher must acquire the right type of knowledge ,skills and abilities to discharge his professional duties and responsibilities efficiently . Different commissions , committees and policies have thrown light on the importance of teacher education .its concerns and issues and recommended measures for revamping and revising teacher education.

Key words; *Teacher education. Pre service teacher education Inservice teacher education*

INTRODUCTION

The teacher is the pivot of any educational system of a country The success and failure of an educational system of a country rest on the teacher .He is the yardstick that measures the achievement and aspiration of the nation .Being the real nation builder ,a teacher must acquire the right type of knowledge ,skills and abilities which helps him to discharge his professional duties and responsibilities in an efficient and effective manner .Teacher education prepares the teachers professionally by reshaping their attitudes habits and personality. According to Kothari Commission competence and character of teachers are the most important factors that contribute to the quality of education and national development .So it is important to secure sufficient supply of high quality recruit to the teaching profession providing the best professional preparation and satisfactory conditions to work .Qualities of a teacher can be best judged mainly on the basis of two factors like personality and professional efficiency of the teacher. Both the qualities are enhanced by teacher education program.

MEANING OF TEACHER EDUCATION

Teacher education or training of teacher means all the program, policies and provisions designed for the prospective teachers to equip them with the required knowledge, skills, attitudes and proficiencies to deliver their duties with efficiency and effectiveness in their respective fields. Teacher education program is organized for various levels of teacher's school, elementary, secondary and higher secondary levels. Teacher education is also for different categories like general teachers, physical education teachers, teachers for children with special needs and college teachers.

There are mainly two types of teacher education program available now a days. These are Pre-Service Teacher Education and Inservice Teacher Education program. In-Service Teacher Education program provides training to the freshers and prepare them professionally for the teaching profession. The Inservice Teacher Education program is designed for the persons who are already in the teaching profession. This program helps to enhance their professional growth and development as a result the teachers will discharge their duties and responsibilities more effectively and efficiently. The changing roles of the teachers in the fast-changing society increase the demands for Inservice Teacher Education for making the teachers smarter than they were before.

Interdisciplinary Approach in the curriculum of Teacher Education Program.

Considering the diversity existing in our society the teacher has to deal with the heterogenous classroom. The technological revolution and globalization are responsible for changing the needs, requirement and aspiration of the students. So, the curriculum of teacher education is interdisciplinary in nature to provide varied opportunities and experiences to the students.

The curriculum of teacher education comprises of four components i.e.

i) Perspectives in Education covers the basics in education, educational psychology, development of child and adolescent, learning and teaching, assessment of learning, contemporary concerns in education and the role of teacher and school, knowledge and curriculum, history and vision of Indian education, planning, management and leadership, creating inclusive classroom etc.

ii) Curriculum and Pedagogic Studies facilitates the pupil teacher to gain knowledge in different school subjects like Biological Science, Physical Science, Mathematics, Social Science, Language etc. This part enables them to develop understanding in the respective content areas and different teaching learning methods and strategies to transact curriculum in the classroom.

iii) Engagement with the field or Practicum part of the curriculum provides sustained engagement with the self, the child, the community and the school at different levels. It is the link between perspective and curriculum and pedagogic studies by providing the pupil-teacher with the real-life situations. School internship program develops the professional capacities and teaching skills.

iv) Enhancing Professional Capacities includes courses in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and its application in the classroom, health, yoga and physical education. These courses focus on the personal and professional identity, art and aesthetic taste of the perspective teachers.

The course structure of the teacher education program is interdisciplinary in nature which ensures both well round and all-round development of the pupil teacher in a holistic manner.

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICIES ON TEACHER EDUCATION

Teachers occupy an honored place in the society. A teacher training program not only put impact on the teachers but also the students of the country. A skilled and well-trained teacher contributes towards the development of thousand students by providing knowledge, fostering critical thinking and serving as a role model. After independence a major concern of the Government of India has been to reconstruct the education system, especially teacher education system for the progress and prosperity of the whole country. There are mainly three National Education Policies promulgated in India after Independence. The first policy is National Policy on Education which was launched during the period of Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968. The second National Policy on Education was promulgated by the Government of India by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986. The third National Education Policy was lunched by the Present Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2020.

NATIONAL POLICY ON EDUCATION 1968 ON TEACHER EDUCATION

Considering the recommendations of Education Commission (1964-66), the government of India lunched the first National Policy on Education in 1968. This policy recommended regarding the important place of the teacher in quality development of education of a country. The personal qualities, character, educational qualification and professional competencies of a teacher determine the success of education of the nation. So, the teacher should be given an honored place in the society. They should be provided proper emoluments with good service conditions considering their qualifications and responsibilities. The teachers should be given academic freedom for pursuing independent studies and doing research activities. This policy gave special emphasis to in-service teacher education program.

NATIONAL POLICY ON EDUCATION 1986 ON TEACHER EDUCATION

The socio - cultural ethos of a country is reflected in the status of a teacher. No person can rise above the level of a teacher. National Policy on Education 1986 has suggested certain measures regarding recruitment of teachers, living and working conditions of teachers elementary and secondary teacher education program. The State Government and the UGC/AICTE should evolve standard method of recruiting teachers basing on the merits and objectivity. A teacher must have love for the children and teaching profession with creativity and commitment to the profession.

The teacher should be provided proper pay and satisfactory allowance at all levels basing on their qualification and professional competencies. Retirement and medical facilities should be available to all the teachers. The teachers from rural and urban areas should avail housing facilities. The posting and transfer of teachers should be made on certain norms.

Teachers 'Associations should be formed to protect the rights and dignity of the teachers. A code of professional ethics for teachers should be prepared by the national level association to maintain the standard of teacher. According to NPE 1986 teacher education is a continuous process and its pre-service and in-service components are inseparable. Pre-service and in-service courses for elementary school teachers are to be organized by District Institute of Education and Training. The colleges of teacher education affiliated to universities should run secondary teacher education program. Both the university and the NCTE should have control over the academic aspect with due reference to quality control. This policy also recommended introduction of 4-year integrated course after the higher secondary stage in addition to usual Bed/Med courses. Regarding the curriculum of teacher education, it suggested an integration of different subjects like education, culture, work experience. Physical education and game and sports with contemporary issues and concerns.

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

Being the first education policy of the 21st century the National Education Policy 2020 aims to revise and revamp all aspects of education structure basing on the traditions and value systems of India in the light of SDG4. Teacher education plays an important role in shaping the next generation of the society. So, the process of teacher preparation requires multidisciplinary approach with development of values and dispositions. Teachers of India should not only be well versed in India's ancient knowledge and traditions, but also in the latest advances in the field of education and pedagogy.

To maintain integrity and credibility in teacher education program the policy recommended to form a Regulatory System empowered to take action against malpractices happening in the system. Educationally sound, multidisciplinary and integrated teacher education courses will exist by 2030. Being multidisciplinary the program requires high quality contents and pedagogy to equip the teachers to face the challenges of the present situations. All teacher education program must run in the composite multidisciplinary institutions having departments of psychology, philosophy, sociology music art etc.

By 2030 the minimal degree qualification for school teachers will be the 4-year integrated Bed which will be a dual major holistic Bachelor's degree both in education and other specialized subject. The Higher Education Institution providing 4-year integrated Bed degree may also provide 2year Bed course to those who have already received a Bachelor's degree in any specialized subject. It may also provide 1 year Bed course to those who have received a 4-year

undergraduate degree. The government should provide scholarship to the meritorious student to attract and encourage them for pursuing teacher education courses.

The National Testing Agency will conduct suitable aptitude test for selecting the candidates for the admission to Pre-service teacher education program to maintain a uniform standard throughout the country.

Necessary initiatives will be taken for continuous professional development of the teachers already in service. The technology platform like SWAYAM/ DIKSHA for online training of teachers will be used for maintaining the standards of teacher education.

CONCLUSION

The National Education Policy 2020 has focused on the problems of teachers and teacher education and suggested measures to ensure quality of teachers at all levels. This policy ensures proper recruitment of teachers, their well preparation and continuous professional development set by the National Professional Standard for Teachers to maintain the standard of the teacher of the country. Being the backbone of the Indian education system teachers shape the future of our country. NEP 2020 equips the teachers with the necessary skills of 21st century and make them true facilitator of learning.

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